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Title: **Forecast of COVID19 infections**

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I have updated the COVID19 infections in EU and USA on May 3rd, publishing the graphs on the following free blogs:

<https://covid19forecast.blogspot.com/>

<https://euocovid19.blogspot.com/>

<https://usacovid19.blogspot.com/>

<https://forbigaio.blogspot.com/>

The same figures are reported here for Italy, EU27 and USA, updated on May 3rd, 2020.

ITALY-COVID19 data and forecast May 4th, 2020

EU COVID19 data and forecast May 4th, 2020

EU COVID19 data and forecast May 4th, 2020

EU COVID19 data and forecast May 4th, 2020

US COVID19 DATA & FORECAST May 4th, 2020

The main conclusion of this analysis is the possibility to forecast the growth of the new infections with the Malthus exponential increase, while the decrease of the new infections follows the Verhulst logistic equation.

The first question is why the trend is different during the increase and the decrease of the new infections?

The second question is who can give an answer?